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ГЕБОТАНИЧЕСКОЕ ИЗУЧЕНИЕ ЛЕКАРСТВЕННЫХ КУСТАРНИКОВ ДАШКЕСЕНСКОГО РАЙОНА

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GEOBOTANICAL STUDY OF MEDICINAL SHRUBS IN THE DASHKESEN DISTRICT

Аннотация:

Учитывая, что сохранение биоразнообразия является одной из актуальных проблем современности, нами были проведены геоботанические исследования с целью сохранения лекарственных деревьев и кустарников в районе Дашкесан. Исследования проводились на высоте 900-1800 м в лесной растительности района Дашкесан.

В ходе исследования в лесной растительности была выявлена I тип растительности, I класс формации, 2 группы формации и 8 ассоциаций. В исследуемой местности типологическое разнообразие составляет, что объясняется богатством дендрофлоры и соответствующим распределением её видов в зависимости от почвенно-климатических условий и рельефа.

В растительном покрове ассоциации Иберийского дуба (*Quercusetum iberica*) встречен лекарственный кустарник - пятилопастный боярышник (*Crataegus pentagyna*). Это растение полезно для питания, производства красителей, нектара, технических и декоративных целей. В лечебных целях используются цветы и плоды боярышника.

В ассоциации *Crataegisetum pentagyna* (пятилопастный боярышник) были зафиксированы виды Кавказского боярышника (*Crataegus caucasica*) и шиповника (*Rosa canina*). Для вида Кавказского боярышника (*Crataegus caucasica*), который подвергается чрезмерной эксплуатации в медицине, рекомендуется принять меры по его охране.

Ассоциация Кавказского граба (*Carpinus caucasica* L.) была обнаружена на высоте 1397 м над уровнем моря (широта: 40031144N; долгота: 45055144E). В составе этой ассоциации также встречаются лекарственные кустарники: узколистная облепиха (*Elaeagnus angustifolium*), ива (*Salix* sp.), черный терн (*Paliurus spinachristi*), облепиха (*Hipporhae rhamnoides*), шиповник (*Rosa* sp.).

Исследования подтверждают, что интенсивное использование приводит к постепенному уничтожению лесов, деградации степей и пастбищ различной степени. В результате наблюдается замедление динамики роста лекарственных растений. Поэтому целью исследований является выяснение причин уничтожения, определение этапа, с которого начинается процесс разрушения, а также устранение или минимизация факторов, способствующих вымиранию или остановке роста.

Abstract:

Given the importance of biodiversity conservation as one of the pressing issues of our time, we have conducted geobotanical studies aimed at preserving medicinally valuable trees and shrubs in the Dashkasan region.

The research was carried out in the forest vegetation type at altitudes ranging from 900 to 1800 meters in the Dashkasan region.

Within the research area, one vegetation type, one formation class, two formation groups, and eight associations were identified in the forest vegetation area. The typological species composition in the research area is diverse, indicating the richness of dendroflora and the distribution of edificators according to soil-climatic conditions and relief.

In the vegetation of the Iberian oak (*Quercus ibérica*) association, the medicinal shrub species *Crataegus pentagyna* was found. This plant is useful for food, dye, nectar, technical, and ornamental purposes. The flowers and fruits of *Crataegus* are used for medicinal purposes.

In the *Crataegus pentagyna* (*Crataegus pentagyna*) association, species such as the Caucasian hawthorn (*Crataegus caucasica*) and the dog rose (*Rosa canina*) were recorded. Due to the excessive exploitation of the Caucasian hawthorn (*Crataegus caucasica*) species in medicine, protective measures are recommended.

The Caucasian hornbeam (*Carpinus caucasica* L.) association was found at an altitude of 1397 meters (lat: 40°31'144"N; long: 45°55'144"E). This association also includes medicinally important shrubs such as narrow-leaved oleaster (*Elaeagnus angustifolium*), willow (*Salix* sp.), Christ's thorn (*Paliurus spinachristi*), sea buckthorn (*Hippophae rhamnoides*), and wild rose (*Rosa* sp.).

The research confirms that intensive use gradually leads to the destruction of forests and the degradation of meadows and pastures to varying degrees. As a result, a slowdown in the growth dynamics of medicinally important plants is observed. Therefore, the purpose of the research is to investigate the causes of destruction, determine the stage at which it begins, and achieve the elimination or reduction of factors that lead to destruction or halt development.

Ключевые слова: лекарственные растения, формация, класс формации, геоботаника

Keywords: medicinal plants, formation, formation class, geobotany

The nature of Azerbaijan is captivating and highly beneficial. Its diverse forests, plains, lakes, rivers, valleys, and mountains are remarkably beautiful. The rich phytocenoses of medicinal plants in Azerbaijan's flora, some of which are unique and not found anywhere else in the world, are truly fascinating. Azerbaijan's medicinal plant resources, which hold significant value, are often exported, leading to the production of new pharmaceutical preparations that are then sold back to us at high prices. Unfortunately, during the transition period, some unscrupulous individuals have exploited nature ruthlessly, harvesting rare and valuable medicinal plants without following proper collection guidelines and selling them in markets for personal gain. Considering all this, it is crucial to conduct a geo-botanical study to ensure the preservation of the medicinal trees and shrubs in the Dashkesen district.

The research was conducted at altitudes of 900-1800 meters within the forest vegetation zone of the Dashkesen district. The systematic position of species was clarified using generally accepted rules, including APG IV ([www. Worldfloraonline.org](http://www.worldfloraonline.org)) [2], World Flora Online (Botanical Journal of the Linnean Society, No 181 (1), pp. 1-20) [1]. The taxonomy and nomenclature of the species were precisely defined. To study the biological characteristics of the species, works such as "Флора Азербайджана," "Флора Кавказа" [5; 6], А.М. Əsgərov's "Plant World" [3], "Conspectus Florae Caucasi" [4], The geo-botanical descriptions of the phytocenoses in which the studied species participate were conducted according to generally accepted methods in geo-botany [7]. Based on this research and field geo-botanical studies, one vegetation type, one formation class, two formation groups, and eight associations were identified in the forest vegetation area of the basin.

In the Dashkesen region, a unique soil-vegetation cover and wildlife have formed due to the ratio of temperature and humidity. Specifically, primitive and peat mountain-meadow soils are found in Murovdag, turf mountain-meadow soils in the highlands, brown mountain-forest soils in the midlands, and dark mountain-meadow and brown mountain-forest soils in the lowlands. The region is also experiencing moderate soil erosion and the formation of ravines.

The vegetation mainly consists of alpine and sub-alpine meadows, as well as broadleaf mountain forests. The broadleaf mountain forest landscape covers slopes at elevations ranging from 600 to 1,900 meters. In the highlands, eastern hornbeam is dominant, while in the midlands, you can find Caucasian hornbeam, eastern oak, linden, maple, elm, hawthorn, ash, forest grape, rowan, common dogwood, plum, medlar, and spindle trees. Coniferous trees and shrubs like black pine and juniper are also present. Along riverbanks, narrow-leaved oleaster, willow, buckthorn, sea buckthorn, and rosehip bushes grow. The main plants in the meadows include Caucasian scabiosa, broad-leaved coral root, elcampane, three-leaf clover, Fischer's bluebell, foxtail, fragrant orchid, primrose, watercress, bilberry, thistle, and others.

The typological species composition in the study area shows diversity, reflecting the richness of the dendroflora and the distribution of edificators in accordance with soil-climatic conditions and relief. The forests under study feature phytocenoses typical of the hornbeam-oak and maple-hornbeam-pine formations, which have formed on meadow-forest and mountain-forest soils at altitudes ranging from 1000 to 2000 meters above sea level. In these areas, forests dominated by oak and hornbeam gradually replace those dominated by pine. Ecological factors play a crucial role in the distribution of forests composed of these trees.

The upper boundary of broadleaf hornbeam-oak forests extends to altitudes of 1800-2000 meters, while the lower boundary is found at 1000-800 meters. Hornbeam forests form groups with both pine and oak forests. In Bayan village of the Dashkesen district, Caucasian hornbeam (*Carpinus betulus*) and Georgian oak (*Quercus iberica*) coexist, creating mixed tall hornbeam-oak forests. In some areas, Georgian oak becomes sparse, and as the altitude reaches 1800 meters, it is replaced by Eastern oak (*Quercus macranthera*).

In the subalpine forests, the broadleaf hornbeam-oak formation class is represented by specific formation groups, including the birch-like hornbeam-Georgian oak association (*Carpinetum betulus-Quercusosum iberica*), hornbeam (*Carpinetum betulus*), Georgian oak (*Quercusetum iberica*) and Eastern oak (*Quercusetum macranthera*) associations. In these areas, the two main dominant oak species are Georgian oak (*Quercus iberica*) and Eastern oak (*Quercus macranthera*).

The vegetation cover of the hornbeam-oak formation is found on brown mountain-forest soils. In the Iberian oak association of the hornbeam-oak (*Carpinetum-Quercusosum*) formation, the monodominant species, Iberian oak (*Quercus iberica* Stev.), has an abundance score of 3-4, a canopy height of 20 meters, and the vegetation cover varies between 80-90%. The herbaceous layer is three-tiered, with an average height of 60-90 cm.

Notably, the plant cover of the Iberian oak (*Quercusetum iberica*) association includes shrubs like five-lobed hawthorn (*Crataegus pentagyna*).

Five-lobed hawthorn (*Crataegus pentagyna*) is a medicinal shrub. It is also used for food, dye, nectar, technical, and ornamental purposes. The flowers and fruits of the hawthorn are used for medicinal purposes. Flowers are collected in May, while fruits are harvested in August-September when fully ripe. The flowers are dried in a shady, well-ventilated area, and the fruits are dried at a temperature of 55-60°C in special dryers. The flowers and fruits contain a range of biologically active substances with medicinal properties, including flavonoids, crataegus, caffeic and chlorogenic acids, essential oils, ascorbic acid, carotene (provitamin A), riboflavin, vitamin B2, the vitamin B group, PP vitamins, organic acids, sugars, proteins, pigments, tannins, and various alkaloid compounds. The leaves and flowers also contain viteskin, saponaretin, orientin, homoorientin, rhamnoside, and 30-38% oil.

In the plant grouping, the rare species Trautvetter's maple (*Acer trautvetteri* Wedw), listed in the "Red Book," is occasionally encountered, with a very low frequency of 1-2 points. Within the species composition of the association, the Iberian oak (*Quercus iberica* Stev.) and the perennial herb large-flowered elecampane (*Inula grandifolia* L.) are endemic to the Caucasus region. Due to the presence of these rare, endemic species, as well as those listed in the "Red Book," it is recommended to implement phytomeliorative ecological measures to ensure their conservation [8].

A formation group dominated by hawthorn (*Crataegus*) and hornbeam (*Carpinus*) has been identified in Bayan village. Research was conducted within the

hawthorn (*Crataegus*) (*Ulmus*) formation group, specifically in the *Crataegusetum* formation class, within the *Crataegusetum pentagyna* (five-lobed hawthorn) association. This association also includes shrub species such as Caucasian hawthorn (*Crataegus caucasica*) and dog rose (*Rosa canina*). Due to the overexploitation of Caucasian hawthorn (*Crataegus caucasica*) in traditional medicine, conservation measures are advised.

The species composition of this association includes 23 plant species, of which 7 species (30.4%) are trees, 7 species (30.4%) are shrubs, and 9 species (39.1%) are perennial herbs. Of these, 9 species (39.1%) are mesophytes, 9 species (39.1%) are mesoxerophytes, and 5 species (24%) are xerophytes.

In the hornbeam-maple formation class, a hornbeam-maple (*Carpinetum-Acerosum*) formation group has developed on mountain-forest soils. The Caucasian hornbeam (*Carpinus caucasica* L.) association was found at an altitude of 1397 meters (latitude: 40°31'44"N; longitude: 45°55'14"E).

The species composition of this association includes 27 species: 6 species (22.2%) are trees, 8 species (29.6%) are shrubs, and 13 species (48.1%) are perennial herbs. Among these, 7 species (21.9%) are mesophytes, 12 species (44.4%) are mesoxerophytes, and 8 species (29.6%) are xerophytes. The dominant species in this phytocoenosis is the Caucasian hornbeam (*Carpinus caucasica* L.), which can reach a height of 12 meters. Along the riverbanks, shrub species such as narrow-leaved oleaster (*Elaeagnus angustifolia*), willow (*Salix* sp.), Christ's thorn (*Paliurus spina-christi*), sea buckthorn (*Hippophae rhamnoides*), and dog rose (*Rosa*) are found. The species *Dianthus armeria* L. is rated with a frequency of 1 point in this plant grouping. The narrow-leaved oleaster (*Elaeagnus angustifolia*), willow (*Salix*), Christ's thorn (*Paliurus spina-christi*), sea buckthorn (*Hippophae rhamnoides*) and dog rose (*Rosa*) species are of medicinal importance. Overexploitation of these medicinal plants can lead to a decrease in their resources.

Research confirms that intensive use gradually leads to the destruction of forests and the degradation of meadows and pastures to varying degrees. This issue has become a significant global problem, drawing the attention of various researchers worldwide. Consequently, the natural or anthropogenic restoration of degraded or degrading formations has become a focus of study. The main goal of this research is to investigate the causes of degradation, determine the stage at which it begins, and work towards eliminating or reducing the factors that lead to destruction or hinder development.

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